

MEDICAL SCIENCES

METHODS OF PREVENTION OF DENTAL DISEASES IN ATHLETES

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Abstract

Dental diseases that occur among athletes require close attention due to the emerging problems associated with dental pathology, which occurs in most cases among athletes whose activities are associated with trauma to the teeth, gums, dentoalveolar joint, and soft tissues of the oral cavity. of the dental profile according to the main evaluation indicators revealed the fact that among athletes involved in various sports, it is necessary to carry out preventive measures for functional disorders and possible pathological changes in the dentoalveolar system. Currently, for this purpose, sports dental splints are used, which ensure the retention of the lower jaw in the position necessary to prevent its injury, with increased pressure arising during training. It should be noted that there are inconveniences, as well as a communicative psychological barrier when using prophylactic splints, this is due to the fact that athletes disrupt the normal closing of the jaws, causing disturbances in diction and cosmetic distortion of the face due to hypertonicity of the masticatory muscles.

Keywords: dental splint, mouthguard, sports dentistry, prevention of injuries and diseases of the dental system

It is known that the problem of health is of particular importance for sports, since it has a direct impact on maintaining the correct integrative response of the body to physical activity, and thus on sports performance and performance [4]. Diseases that occur in athletes are not the result of sports training, but occur with the combined effect of certain risk factors. Their comprehensive study, identification, prevention and elimination is an urgent task of modern medicine, the solution of which will allow maintaining health even in the conditions of the most intense training, increasing sports performance, and strengthening the social significance of sports [4]. After all, sport, as a socially active branch of human activity, is undergoing its changes in the direction of progress. Every year the number of different sports and the number of adherents of an active lifestyle increases. In this regard, timely diagnosis and rational prevention of dental diseases in representatives of different sports is of utmost importance, which should be carried out according to the principles of complexity, continuity, consistency, and mandatory individualization. One of the factors contributing to the dental morbidity of athletes is excessive physical activity [8]. Despite the fact that a strictly balanced system of physical activity, rest, nutrition, means of recovery and rehabilitation is of current importance, in the conditions of competitive activity it is far from always possible to avoid overload and overwork. This is fraught

with the development of overtraining syndrome - a phenomenon that affects not only the effectiveness of the training process, but also the health of the athlete as a whole. As a result, a functional overload of the craniomandibular system develops, as a result of which the teeth, periodontium, muscles and temporomandibular joints experience increased stress. Also, overtraining syndrome disrupts electrolyte metabolism in athletes, there is a decrease in the number of energy substrates, there is a loss of calcium, phosphorus, potassium and especially fluorine salts by the body, the lack of which contributes to the occurrence of a carious process [1], [2]. Athletes, in comparison with their non-athlete peers, are more likely to have anomalies of the teeth and jaws, and the prevalence and intensity of caries are higher [7], [8]. The next most important risk factor is increased traumatism [6]. According to statistics, 10% of dental injuries were obtained during sports events [5]. Therefore, the main links of activities [5]. Therefore, the main links in the prevention of health disorders in the maxillofacial region at the individual level under the influence of harmful and dangerous occupational factors are preliminary medical and mandatory periodic medical examinations. With their help, a dentist will be able to determine the need for an athlete in preventive measures and prescribe appropriate treatment. mandibular system and protection of the maxillofacial region from damage. In professional sports, sports mouth

guards are used quite widely, and for people involved in sports at the amateur level, they are rarely recommended. As a result of low awareness of the population, mouth guards are practically not used during physical education and amateur sports, thereby significantly increasing the risk of maxillofacial injuries. increased load; the impossibility of using the structure in athletes with pathology of hard dental tissues; rather large sizes, which violates diction, causes dyspnea, a gag reflex, which contribute to the emergence of a communication barrier [3]. Conventionally, sports mouth guards can be divided into three types: semi-professional, professional, elite. The most popular trademarks are "Signache" and "Paugard". Most traditional boxing splint designs are made from flexible plastics. Mouthguards are produced in the USA, Canada, Australia and the UK based on the concept of neuromuscular dentistry developed by Dr. Bernard Jankelson (1969). This science studies the interaction of the components of the cranio-mandibular system and aims to improve the interaction between them. In 1978, Dr. Steve Smith established that there was a relationship between the position of the lower jaw and the ability of the arm muscles to contract strongly. In the studies of Richard Kaufman (1980) it was shown that increasing the bite to a certain individual height gives the athlete greater strength and endurance when performing. It was also noted that under the same conditions, there is a decrease in the number of injuries and a decrease in their severity. Based on the results of an experiment to study the effect of MORA (2002) (mandibular orthopedic repositioning appliance - an orthopedic device for changing the position of the lower jaw), scientists have established a relationship between the position of the lower jaw and isometric muscle strength. It is very important that thanks to neuromuscular sports mouth guards, optimal occlusion is achieved, the TMJ area is decompressed (this zone is closely connected with the balance organ - the "labyrinth" of the inner ear) and the athlete's ability to maintain balance increases. In the course of studying the problem of using sports dental splints we noted that most professional and non-professional athletes ignore their use, considering it the prerogative of boxers who are required to wear splints during fights and training. Sports fans explain this by the fact that these designs have a number of disadvantages. We used a tire, the essence of the technology of which is the use of an elastic material subjected to thermoforming. The structure is made of two layers of elastic material, between which a soft layer of silicone material is additionally introduced on the chewing surface of the tire. Material "Drufosoft" in terms of chemical composition is an ethyl and vinyl acetate copolymer, it has good mechanical properties and low water absorption. The presented properties are insufficient to neutralize the increased pressure that occurs at the time of reflex compression of the jaws during power sports, so an additional layer of silicone material was introduced, self-polymerizing during the cold curing process. Chemically, A-silicones are vinyl polysiloxanes. They have a lower percentage of distortions (permanent deformations) in relation to any other existing ones, demonstrate good dimensional stability. The use of this

design provides maximum unloading of the cranio-mandibular system due to the presence of the following structural elements: imprints of antagonist teeth tubercles on the chewing surface of the splint, which hold the lower jaw in the correct centric position at the time of loading; a soft layer of silicone material located on the chewing surface between two layers of elastic material, which, by neutralizing the increased load, prevents the development of masticatory muscle hypertonicity; jumpers in the form of an arc connecting the bases of the tire, which does not impede breathing and plays the role of a barrier for the tongue; formed gap between the incisors and canines, which protects the teeth from damage associated with overload. This sports splint can be used by athletes with a large number of restored teeth. By reducing the size of the structure, hygiene, satisfactory diction and aesthetics of the face are ensured; the occurrence of a gag reflex is excluded, due to which there are no communication barriers. An important advantage is the simplicity and comfort of using a sports mouthguard. A sports dental splint is obtained as follows: anatomical impressions are taken from the upper and lower jaws with an alginate impression mass, plaster models are cast on the impressions, the boundaries of the future splint are marked on the model of the upper jaw: from the side of the vestibule of the oral cavity, the edge the basis is located below the transitional fold by 2 mm; covers the premolars, first and second molars of the upper jaw. The tire covers the anterior third of the hard palate and the alveolar processes, leaving the palatine suture, vestibular and palatine surfaces of the frontal group of teeth of the upper jaw free. The first tire layer is then made in a thermoformer by applying a layer of elastic material. Next, the models are plastered in an occluder (achieving a tight closure of the teeth). A soft lining is applied to the chewing surface of the dental splint; when the models are closed, imprints of the antagonist teeth of the lower jaw remain on it. The maxillary model is removed from the occluder and a second layer of material is applied in the thermoformer. Next, the model of the upper jaw is again plastered into the occluder. The chewing surface of the tooth splint is heated, the models close under pressure and thus pronounced imprints of the supporting tubercles of the antagonist teeth (1.5-3.0 mm deep) are formed.

Findings

Thus, the analysis of the results, studies conducted by foreign and domestic scientists showed that the urgent task of modern medicine is a comprehensive study, identification, prevention and elimination of risk factors for the development of dental pathology in athletes. The use of the developed design of a sports mouth guard allows to stabilize the state of the cranio-mandibular system in unfavorable conditions for it. The wider use of mouth guards by athletes will ensure the prevention of diseases of the hard tissues of the teeth, periodontium and temporomandibular joint and will significantly reduce the risk of pathological changes in the dentoalveolar system.

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